

THE CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES AND DEVELOPMENTAL PROSPECTS OF TRANSITIONING TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

G.P.Erkaeva

Karshi State university, professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15383707>

Abstract. *The article describes the importance and necessity of transition to a green economy using stages of development. The indicators of the amount of emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2010-2023 are analyzed. Prospective directions of development of a green economy in the country are substantiated.*

Keywords: *green economy, ecology, atmosphere, pollutant, Rio Declaration, Kyoto Protocol, Paris Agreement, strategy.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishning ahamiyati va zarurati rivojlanish bosqichlari yordamida ifodalangan. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2010-2023 yillar davomida atmosferaga chiqarilgan ifloslantiruvchi moddalar miqdori ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilingan. Mamlakatda yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari asoslangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *yashil iqtisodiyot, ekologiya, atmosfera, ifloslantiruvchi modda, Rio deklaratsiyasi, Kioto protokoli, Parij iqlim kelishuvi, strategiya.*

Аннотация. *В статье описывается важность и необходимость перехода к зеленой экономике с использованием этапов развития. Проанализированы показатели количества выбросов загрязняющих веществ в атмосферу Республики Узбекистан за 2010-2023 годы. Обоснованы перспективные направления развития зеленой экономики в стране.*

Ключевые слова: *зеленая экономика, экология, атмосфера, загрязняющее вещество, Рио-де-Жанейрская декларация, Киотский протокол, Парижское соглашение, стратегия.*

Introduction. Today, climate of globalization, the rapid development of industry and the misuse of natural resources are releasing large amounts of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, causing significant damage to the environment. As a result, global climate change is occurring. As part of the Paris Agreement, Uzbekistan confirms its commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 35% of GDP by 2030. To achieve this goal, the "Strategy of the Transition to a "Green" Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2030" was adopted [1]. As a result, it is planned to double energy efficiency, increase the share of renewable energy sources to more than 25%, modernize the infrastructure of industrial enterprises to increase their energy efficiency by at least 20%, and apply environmentally friendly technologies to industrial processes.

Literature review. Theoretical and practical issues related to the development of a green economy have been studied by many scientists and researchers. This research is closely related to socio-economic issues such as energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, resource conservation, and environmental protection. In particular, the studies of foreign scientists such as S. Beder, G. D. Sweeney, Herman Daly, Joshua Farley, Robert Costanza, David Stern, Marcus Hagedorn, Tim Jackson express their views on the theoretical foundations, potential, dimensions, problems and ways to solve them of the green economy. Also, important studies on the green economy by scientists from the CIS countries such as V. Frolov, A. Shevchuk, A. Lebedev, N.

Grigoryeva, Y. Danilov can be cited. Their research studies include the foundations, principles, models, mechanisms of the green economy, prospects for their implementation of energy-efficient technologies, the impact of the green economy on sustainable economic growth. Local scientists and researchers A.Vakhabov, Sh.Khajibakiyev, A.A.Isadjonov, Z.Nurov, N.I.Abdurakhmonov, Sh.A.Sultanov, M.M.Khamdamov have conducted important studies on the development of the green economy in Uzbekistan. However, it should be recognized that the identification and description of the main theories and concepts related to the green economy and their connection with sustainability have not yet been fully resolved. Therefore, the analysis of important factors for the development of the green economy in our country is relevant.

Research methodology. The study was based on the relevant resolutions and decrees of the President and Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the “Strategy for Transition to a Green Economy” and the documents of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). Data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used. The study used induction and deduction, a systematic approach, logical and comparative methods of analysis, and statistical analysis methods.

Results. One of the main directions of a sustainable economy is the green economy, which covers the areas of environmental, energy and technological development. Green Economy is a model of economic reorganization in order to achieve environmental sustainability. Its main goal is to reduce environmental impact, use resources efficiently, and ensure a balance between economic growth and environmental sustainability. Green economy involves the application of environmental measures in energy, transport, industry, agriculture and other sectors.

The formation of the concept of a green economy can be divided into several stages. Although the first stage of research aimed at developing a green economy is reported to have occurred in the 1950s-1980s [4,9], many note that the first stage falls on the 1970s. During this period, environmental problems began to be discussed at a global level. The Stockholm Environmental Conference, organized by the United Nations (UN) in 1972, was important in drawing attention to the connection between ecology and economy, and the principles of ecosystem and sustainable development were formed at this stage [3]. The period from 1980 to 2000, associated with the increased attention to the green economy, can be recognized as the period of the second stage. This stage is significant for the formation and development of new economic models that integrate the issues of resource efficiency with environmental protection. In 1987, the UN developed the "Sustainable Development Concept", which aims to ensure a balance between nature, ecosystems, and economic development, and to preserve resources for the needs of future generations. This concept was recognized globally, and economic growth models aimed at ensuring environmental sustainability began to be created, and important documents such as the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development and the Kyoto Protocol were adopted internationally.

The global transition to a green economy, which has been ongoing since the 2000s and will continue until approximately the 2030s, can be recognized as the third stage. In economic literature, this stage is called the “Transition to sustainable economic transformation”. The importance of this stage is reflected in the ecological and social sustainability of economic development, that is, in its focus on responding to complex solutions to social, environmental and economic problems. In 2015, the Paris Climate Agreement was signed, which set a goal for all participating countries to combat climate change by reducing carbon emissions into the atmosphere and limiting global warming to 1.5-2.0 degrees Celsius. According to analyses, the

total volume of emissions into the atmosphere on our planet by 2030 could reach 55 gigatons. To keep the temperature within 1.5-2 degrees, the amount of emissions should not exceed 40 gigatons. Therefore, within the framework of the Paris Agreement, strategies and measures were discussed to provide financial and technical assistance to developing, poor and environmentally challenged countries, as well as to create renewable energy sources. Also in September of this year, the 70th UN General Assembly adopted the “2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development-SDGs”. This document sets out 17 global sustainable development goals and 169 specific targets, covering issues of ensuring global social, economic and environmental sustainability by 2030. Uzbekistan joined the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change in 1993, signed the Kyoto Protocol in 1999, and the Paris Agreement in 2017. The first environmental problems and concepts in Uzbekistan began to emerge in the 1950s, as a result of the drying up of the Aral Sea. The Paris Agreement provides an opportunity to combat the negative consequences of the Aral Sea ecological crisis, environmental pollution, desertification, drought, climate change, and attract international cooperation, climate grants, and other investment resources [2]. In line with the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), the country has made a quantitative commitment to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions per unit of gross domestic product by 10 percent below 2010 levels by 2030, and is making significant efforts to achieve this. The figure below shows an analysis of the amount of toxic substances emitted into the atmosphere in the country from 2010 to 2023.

Figure 1: Amount of pollutants emitted into the atmosphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan during 2010-2023 (thousand tons)

As can be seen, the emission of pollutants into the atmosphere was not uniform. In 2010, the amount of harmful substances was at its lowest level (729 thousand tons), while in 2014 it reached its highest level, amounting to 1,162.1 thousand tons. In 2015, this figure decreased by 17%, while in 2016 it increased by 3.0%. In the next two years (2017 and 2018), the emission of pollutants into the atmosphere decreased relatively, and in 2019, there was a sharp increase again, and then a downward trend was observed in the subsequent periods. The observation of such an unstable trend over the past 24 years is associated with a number of factors that have not reduced atmospheric pollutants to the expected level, including the development of the industrial sector,

the growth of motor transport, changes in energy sources and technologies, as well as environmental standards and methodologies.

The rapid development of the industrial sector in Uzbekistan, especially the energy, metallurgy and chemical industries, has led to increased emissions of toxic gases into the atmosphere during these periods. According to data, the main sectors that have an impact on the atmosphere are thermal power plants and cement production enterprises. In 2022, 40% of emissions were accounted for by oil and gas, 22.8% by energy, 21.2% by metallurgy, 2.8% by construction, and 11.7% by other sectors.

Today, our country is taking consistent institutional and organizational measures to ensure environmental safety. It is worth noting that the sustainable development of the country's economy, first of all, directly depends on the development and implementation of a strategy of structural and institutional changes, taking into account environmental processes occurring at the global, national and local levels. It is worth noting that today in Uzbekistan a legal framework has been created aimed at the rational use of natural resources without harming the environment and protecting the health of the population, and in accordance with relevant international norms. The Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the transition to a "green" economy for the period 2019-2030 has been adopted. According to it, the basic sectors of the economy are to increase energy efficiency; diversify the consumption of energy resources and develop the use of renewable energy sources; adapt to and mitigate the consequences of climate change, increase the efficiency of the use of natural resources and preserve natural ecosystems; The development of financial and non-financial mechanisms to support the "green" economy were identified as priority areas of the strategy. Through the implementation of the strategy for transition to a green economy, it is planned to achieve the following results by 2030 (Table 1).

Table 1

Target indicators of the strategy for transition to a "green" economy in Uzbekistan by 2030

№	Indicators	Unit of measurement	Expected result in 2030
1	Relative greenhouse gas emissions compared to 2010	%	35 percent reduction
2	Renewable energy generation capacity	GW	Increase to 15 GW
3	Share of renewable energy sources in electricity generation	%	Increase by more than 30 percent
4	Energy efficiency in industry	%	20 percent
5	Introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies	ha	1 million hectares
6	Green zones	%	30 percent
7	Forest fund reserves indicators	meter/cubic meter	90 million
8	Solid waste recycling	%	Increase from 65 percent

For comparison, in Uzbekistan in 2020 the share of renewable energy sources (solar, wind, water, biomass energy and geothermal energy) was 3%, and 97% of the country's total energy needs were covered by natural gas and carbon sources. In 2020, Uzbekistan emitted about 208 million tons of greenhouse gases (CO₂), of which the energy and transport sector accounted for

about 61%. 85% of the water consumed in our country comes from transboundary sources, that is, from abroad. 90 percent of water resources are used in agriculture. According to experts, climate change and the construction of the Kushtepa Canal in Afghanistan could reduce the Amu Darya basin by about 30 percent by 2030. The total water deficit due to the Kushtepa Canal and climate change could reach 18.9 percent in 2028 and 29.4 percent in 2030 [10], which would create serious problems in our country and its regions due to the problem of water scarcity. Therefore, the introduction of innovative water-saving irrigation technologies is urgent. In Uzbekistan, the area covered by water-saving technologies was 28 thousand hectares in 2017, and in 2024 it was increased to 1.9 million hectares, including 561 thousand hectares of drip irrigation. This year, 2 billion cubic meters of water were saved due to the use of energy-saving technologies.

Conclusion. The transition to a green economy in Uzbekistan can be assessed as the result of long-term economic development trends. For a long time, inefficient use of land and water resources in agriculture, lack of waste disposal, rapid development of industrial sectors, and accelerated urbanization processes have led to a disruption of the ecological balance.

This creates the need to transition to new economic models based on the principles of a green economy in the use of resources, which is one of the main conditions for sustainable development in our country. The following can be recognized as prospects for the transition to a green economy in Uzbekistan:

- Improving the national legislative framework and strategic programs aimed at protecting the environment and reducing carbon emissions;
- Introducing innovative technologies for increasing energy efficiency, recycling waste, and using renewable energy sources;
- Increasing investments in the production of solar, wind, and biomass energy for the production of renewable energy sources;
- Introducing modern agrotechnologies for agriculture, reducing this problem through water-saving systems;
- Implementing practical measures to increase the ecological literacy of the population and train specialists in the green economy;
- Increasing the number of "green spaces" and protected natural zones in our country to reduce the negative consequences of climate change.

The formation and development of a green economy is carried out in a number of stages, in which global environmental problems, economic development and actions aimed at sustainability are inextricably linked. The transition to a green economy depends on each country's own adaptation strategy, the results of which will help to preserve the environment and create conditions for sustainable development for the population. To achieve these goals, the efforts of the public and private sectors to minimize production and environmental risks play an important role.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan." On approval of the Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the transition to a "green" economy for the period 2019-2030". October 4, 2019, No. PD-4477. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4539502>.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Ratification of the Paris Agreement (Paris, December 12, 2015)" dated October 2, 2018, No. LRU-491
3. United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, 5-16 June 1972, Stockholm.

4. G. D. Sweeney . "The Green Economy Reader: Lessons in the Transition to a Sustainable World" (, 2013).
5. Robert Costanza. "The Value of the World's Ecosystem Services and Natural Capital"// Nature, 1997
6. Markus Hagedorn. "Green Economy: A Sustainable Development Agenda" // Springer, 2016
7. Tim Jackson. "Prosperity Without Growth: Economics for a Finite Planet"// Routledge, 2009
8. A.V.Vaxabov, Sh.X.Xajibakiyev va b. Yashil iqtisodiyot: Darslik / –Toshkent.: Universitet”, 2020. -262 b.
9. Gulbakhor, E. (2023). Possibilities of increasing the standard of living of the population of the regions in socio-economic development. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(9), 412-416.
10. Shukurov, U. S. PECULIARITIES OF INDUSTRIAL LOCATION IN CITIES AND DISTRICTS OF KASHKADARYA REGION. *GWALIOR MANAGEMENT ACADEMY*, 73.